

L'Empire de la supervision
Capture des savoirs et gouvernement colonial
dans l'Inde britannique

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Bibliographie

Archives

British Library, London

INDIA OFFICE RECORDS

Bengal Civil Judicial Proceedings

Bengal Law Consultations

Bengal Proceedings

Bengal Public Consultations

Board's Collections

Murshidabad: Proceedings of Provincial Council of Revenue

Home Miscellaneous

Judicial Letters Received from Bengal

ADDITIONAL MANUSCRIPTS

Warren Hastings Papers

Elijah Impey Papers

Wellesley Papers

EUROPEAN MANUSCRIPTS

Henry Thomas Colebrooke Papers

George Bogle Papers

National Library of Wales, Aberystwyth

JONES William, *A Manuscript Volume (wholly in English), Containing Questions to the Pundits, etc., and Their Answers in Connection to Various Legal Cases, MS. 5476D*, Aberystwyth, National Library of Wales, 1786.

Victoria Memorial Hall, Kolkata

The Judicial Notebooks of John Hyde and Sir Robert Chambers, numérisés.

National Library, Kolkata

The Judicial Notebooks of John Hyde and Sir Robert Chambers, microfilm.

West Bengal State Archives, Kolkata

Judicial Records

Beinecke Library, Yale, New Haven

William Jones's Manuscript Notebook, 1785.

Corpus

A. B., *A Letter to the Right Honourable Lord North on the Present Proceedings Concerning the East-India Company*, London, J. Dodsley, 1773.

ALI Karam, « The Muzaffarnama », in *Bengal Nawābs*, traduit par Jadunath SARKAR, Calcutta, Asiatic Society, 1952.

ANONYME, *A Concise View of the Charges Against Sir Elijah Impey, with Reflections on His Conduct While Chief Justice in India*, London, J. Debrett, 1788.

ANONYME, *A Review of the Principles and Conduct of the Judges of His Majesty's Supreme Court of Judicature in Bengal: Or, an Enquiry into the Causes That Have Obstructed or Defeated the Salutary Ends Proposed by the Legislature in Establishing This Court*, London, 1782.

ANONYME, *Thoughts on Improving the Government of the British Territorial Possessions in the East Indies*, London, T. Cadell, 1780.

ANONYME, « Observations Upon the Administration of Justice in Bengal; Occasioned by Some Late Proceedings at Dacca », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

ANONYME, « Narrative of the Proceedings of the Provincial Council at Patna in the Suit of Behader Beg Against Nadara Begum: And of the Supreme Court of Judicature at Calcutta, in the Suit of Nadara Begum Against Bahader Beg and Others, and in the Criminal Prosecution Instituted Against Nadara Begum and Her Accomplices for Forgery: Forming Together What Is Generally Called in Bengal the Patna Cause », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

ANONYME, *An Essay on the Rights of the East India Company to the Perpetuity of Their Trade, Possessions and Revenues in India*, London, Thomas Payne, 1776.

ANONYME, *The Present State of the British Interest in India: With a Plan for Establishing a Regular System of Government in That Country*, London, J. Almon, 1773.

ANONYME, *A Letter to the Proprietors of East-India-Stock, on the Subject of Sending Supervisors with Extraordinary Powers to India. By a Friend to Fair Discussion*, London, S. Bladon, 1772.

ANONYME, *A Letter to the Right Honourable Lord North; on the East-India Bill Now Depending in Parliament*, London, J. Almon, and Brotherton & Sewell, 1772.

ANONYME, *A Plan for the Government of the Provinces of Bengal. Addressed to the Directors of the East India Company*, London, J. Wilkie, 1772.

ANONYME, *The True Alarm*, London, Printed for the Author, 1770.

ANONYME, *The Importance of the British Dominion in India, Compared with that in America*, London, J. Almon, 1770.

ANONYME, *The Conduct of the East-India Company, with Respect to Their Wars, &c.*, London, 1767.

ANONYME, *Reflections on the Present State of Our East India Affairs. By a Gentleman Long Resident in India*, London, T. Lownds, 1764.

ANONYME [A Proprietor], *A Letter to a Late Popular Director, Relative to India Affairs, and the Present Contests*, London, G. Kearsley, 1769.

ANONYME [Alexander Dalrymple], *A General View of the East-India Company, Written in January, 1769. To Which Are Added, Some Observations on the Present State of Their Affairs*, London, J. Nourse, P. Elmsly, Brotherton & Sewell, J. Robson, S. Leacroft, 1772.

ANONYME [Alexander Dalrymple], *Considerations on a Pamphlet, Entitled « Thoughts on Our Acquisitions in the East-Indies, Particularly Respecting Bengal »*, London, J. Nourse, P. Elmsly, Brotherton & Sewell, J. Robson, 1772.

ANONYME [Alexander Dalrymple], *A Second Letter Concerning the Proposed Supervisorship*, London, Richardson & Urquhart, 1769.

ANONYME [Alexander Dalrymple], *A Letter to the Court of Directors... Concerning the Proposed Supervisorship*, London, Richardson & Urquhart, 1769.

ANONYME [George Johnstone], *Thoughts on Our Acquisitions in the East Indies: Particularly Respecting Bengal*, London, T. Becket and P.A. De Hondt, 1771.

ANONYME [Nathaniel Smith], *General Remarks on the System of Government in India*, London, J. Nourse, 1773.

ANONYME [Nathaniel Smith], *Observations on the Present State of the East India Company; and on the Measures to Be Pursued for Ensuring Its Permanency, and Augmenting Its Commerce*, London, J. Nourse, 1771.

ANONYME [Philip Francis], *Extract of an Original Letter from Calcutta, Relative to the Administration of Justice by Sir E. Impey*, London, J. Debrett, 1781.

ANONYME [Warren Hastings], *A Proposal for Establishing a Professorship of the Persian Language in the University of Oxford*, 1767.

ANQUETIL-DUPERRON Abraham-Hyacinthe, *Législation orientale*, Amsterdam, Marc-Michel Rey, 1778.

ARISTOTE, *Les Politiques*, traduit par Pierre PELLEGRIN, Paris, Flammarion, 1990.

BOLTS William, *Considerations on India Affairs; Particularly Respecting the Present State of Bengal and Its Dependencies*, London, J. Almon, P. Elmsly & Brotherton and Sewell, 1772.

BOUCHET, J.V., « Lettre du Père Bouchet, 2 oct. 1714 », in COMPAGNIE DE JÉSUS, *Lettres édifiantes et curieuses: écrites des missions étrangères*, Paris, Nicolas Le Clerc, 1720, vol.14.

BRUCE John, *Historical View of Plans, for the Government of British India, and Regulation of Trade to the East Indies: And Outlines of a Plan of Foreign Government, of Commercial Economy, and of Domestic Administration, for the Asiatic Interests of Great Britain*, London, J. Sewell & J. Debrett, 1793.

COBBETT William (dir.), *The Parliamentary History of England from the Earliest Period to the Year 1803*, London, T. C. Hansard, 1814, vol.22.

COBBETT William (dir.), *The Parliamentary History of England from the Earliest Period to the Year 1803*, London, T. C. Hansard, 1814, vol.21.

COBBETT William (dir.), *The Parliamentary History of England from the Earliest Period to the Year 1803*, T. C. Hansard, 1813, vol.17.

COLEBROOKE Henry T., « Account of the Hindu Schools of Law », in *Hindu Law*, 1, London, Parbury, Allen & Co., 1830, pp. 315-320.

COLEBROOKE Henry T., *Two Treatises on the Hindu Law of Inheritance*, Calcutta, Printed by A. H. Hubbard, at the Hindoostanee Press, 1810.

COLEBROOKE Henry T., « Preface », in *A Digest of Hindu Law on Contracts and Successions*, Calcutta, Printed at the Honourable Company's Press, 1798.

COLEBROOKE Thomas E., *The Life of H.T. Colebrooke*, London, Trübner, 1873.

COMMITTEE OF SECRECY, *Reports from Committees of the House of Commons, Vol. IV- East Indies, 1772-1773, First-Ninth Report*, London, House of Commons, 1804 [1773].

CLIVE Robert, *Lord Clive's Speech in the House of Commons*, London, 1772.

DOW Alexander, *The History of Hindostan*, London, T. Becket and P. A. De Hondt, 1772, vol.3.

DOW Alexander, *The History of Hindostan*, 2^e éd., London, T. Becket and P. A. De Hondt, 1770 [1768], vol.2.

DOW Alexander, *The History of Hindostan, Translated from the Persian*, 2nd éd., London, T. Becket and P. A. De Hondt, 1770 [1768], vol.1.

EUMENES, *A Plan for the Government of Bengal, and for the Protection of the Other British Settlements in the East Indies: In a Letter to the Right Honourable Lord North, First Lord of the Treasury, &c.*, London, J. Almon, 1772.

FOOTE Samuel, *The Nabob*, London, T. Cadell, 1778 [1772].

FRANCIS Philip, *Letter from Mr. Francis to Lord North, late Earl of Guildford*, London, J. Debrett, 1793.

GANDHI Mohandas Karamchand, *Hind Swaraj - L'émancipation à l'indienne*, traduit par Annie MONTAUT, Paris - Nantes, Fayard, 2014 [1909].

GLEIG George Robert, *Memoirs of the Life of the Right Hon. Warren Hastings, first Governor-General of Bengal*, London, Richard Bentley, 1841, vol.1.

GOLDSTÜCKER Theodor, *On the Deficiencies in the Present Administration of Hindu Law*, London, Trübner and Co, 1871.

HALHED Nathaniel Brassey, « Preface », in *A Code of Gentoo Laws*, London, 1776.

HALHED Nathaniel Brassey (dir.), *A Code of Gentoo Laws, or Ordinations of the Pundits*, London, 1776.

HAMILTON Alexander, « Review of Mark Wilks' Historical Sketches of the South of India », *Edinburgh Review*, 1811, vol. 18, n° 36, pp. 343-370.

HAMILTON Alexander, « Review of A Grammar of the Sanskrita Language by Charles Wilkins », *The Edinburgh Review*, 1809, vol. 13, pp. 366-381.

HASTINGS Warren, « Letter to Nathaniel Smith », in *Bhāgvāt-Geētā, or Dialogues of Krēṣhṇā and Ārjōṅ*, C. Nourse, 1785.

HASTINGS Warren, « Minute of the Honorable the Governor-General, 2d June 1783 », in *Ayeen Akbery: or, the Institutes of the Emperor Akber*, traduit par Francis GLADWIN, Calcutta, 1783.

HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Principes de la philosophie du droit*, traduit par Jean-François KERVÉGAN, Paris, Presses Universitaires de France, 2013 [1820].

HOUSE OF COMMONS, *House of Commons Sessional Papers of the Eighteenth Century*, Wilmington, Del., Scholarly Resources Inc., 1975, vol.33.

HOUSE OF COMMONS, *Report from the Select Committee on the Affairs of the East India Company*, 1831.

HOUSE OF COMMONS, *Reports from Committees of the House of Commons. Vol. VI, East Indies, 1783: Reports on the Administration of Justice, &c. in the East Indies*, London, House of Commons, 1806.

HOUSE OF COMMONS, *Reports from Committees of the House of Commons. Vol. V. East Indies, 1781-1782*, London, House of Commons, 1804.

IMPEY Elijah, *The Speech of Sir Elijah Impey, Late Chief Justice of the Supreme Court of Judicature at Fort William in Bengal. Delivered by Him at the Bar of the House of Commons, on the Fourth Day of February 1788*, London, John Stockdale, 1788.

IMPEY Elijah Barwell, *Memoirs of Sir Elijah Impey, Knt., First Chief Justice of the Supreme Court of Judicature, at Fort William, Bengal*, London, D. Batten, 1857.

JIMŪTAVĀHANA, *Jimūtavāhana's Dayabhaga: The Hindu Law of Inheritance in Bengal*, New York - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2002.

JOLLY Julius, *Outlines of an History of the Hindu Law of Partition, Inheritance, and Adoption: as Contained in the Original Sanskrit Treatises*, Calcutta, Thacker, Spink & Co., 1885.

JONES William, *The Letters of Sir William Jones*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1970, 2 vol.

JONES William, *The Works of Sir William Jones*, London, J. Stockdale & J. Walker, 1807, 13 vol.

JUSTINIEN, *Le Digeste ou Pandectes de l'Empereur Justinien*, Paris, Bouglé, 1803, vol.1.

LOCKE John, *Le Second traité du gouvernement*, traduit par Jean-Fabien SPITZ et Christian LAZZERI, Paris, Presses Universitaires de France, 1994 [1689].

MACNAGHTEN Francis Workman, *Considerations on the Hindoo Law, as It Is Current in Bengal*, Serampore, Mission Press, 1824.

MACNAGHTEN William Hay, *Principles and Precedents of Hindu Law*, Calcutta, Baptist Mission Press, 1828.

MACNAGHTEN William Hay (dir.), *Reports of Cases Determined in the Court of Sudder Dewanny Adawlut*, Calcutta, Printed at Bishop's College Press, by H. Townsend, 1827, vol.1.

MACPHERSON David, *Annals of Commerce, Manufactures, Fisheries, and Navigation*, London, Nichols and son et alii., 1805, vol.1.

MAINE Henry Sumner, *Ancient Law: its Connections with the Early History of Society and its Relation to Modern Ideas*, London, John Murray, 1861.

MARX Karl, « The British Rule in India », *New-York Daily Tribune*, 25/06/1853.

MAYNE John D., « Introduction », in Thomas STRANGE, *Hindu Law*, 4^e éd., Madras, J. Higginbotham, 1864.

MICKLE William J., « Introduction », in *The Lusiad or, the Discovery of India*, 2^e éd., Oxford, Jackson and Lister, 1778.

MILL James, *The History of British India*, Baldwin, Cradock, and Joy, 1817, vol.2.

MILL James, *The History of British India*, Baldwin, Cradock, and Joy, 1817, vol.1.

MILL John Stuart, *Writings on India*, Toronto, University of Toronto Press, 1990.

MONTESQUIEU Charles-Louis de Secondat, *De l'Esprit des lois*, Paris, GF-Flammarion, 1993 [1748], vol.2.

MONTESQUIEU Charles-Louis de Secondat, *De l'Esprit des lois*, Paris, GF-Flammarion, 1993 [1748], vol.1.

NANDA PAṆḌITA et DEVANĀDA-BHAṬṬA, *The Dattaka-Mimānsā and Dattaka-Chandrikā, Two Original Treatises on the Hindu Law of Adoption*, traduit par James C. C. SUTHERLAND, Calcutta, Printed by Philip Pereira at the Hindoostanee Press, 1821.

NEHRU Jawaharlal, *The Discovery of India*, Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1989 [1946].

NELSON James H., *A View of the Hindū Law as Administered by the High Court of Judicature at Madras*, Madras - Calcutta - Bombay, Higginbotham & Co, 1877.

NORTON John Bruce, *The Administration of Justice in Southern India*, Madras - London, Pharaoh and Co - Stevens & Norton, 1853.

OLIVELLE Patrick (dir.), *Manu's Code of Law: a Critical Edition and Translation of the Mānava-Dharmaśāstra*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005.

ORME Robert, *Historical Fragments of the Mogul Empire, of the Morattoes, and of the English Concerns in Indostan*, 2^e éd., London, F. Wingrave, 1785.

PONS Jean-François, « Lettre au Père du Halde, 23 novembre 1740 », in COMPAGNIE DE JÉSUS, *Lettres édifiantes et curieuses, écrites des Missions étrangères, par quelques missionnaires de la Compagnie de Jésus*, Paris, P.-G. Le Mercier et Marc Bordelet, 1743, vol.26, pp. 218-256.

POWELL Thomas, *The Right, Interest, and Duty, of the State, as Concerned in the Affairs of the East Indies*, London, S. Bladon, 1773.

RABAUT SAINT-ÉTIENNE Jean-Paul, *Considérations sur les intérêts du tiers-état : adressées au peuple des provinces*, 1788.

ROUSSEAU Jean-Jacques, *Du Contrat social*, Paris, Flammarion, 2001 [1762].

ROY Rammohun, *Brief Remarks Regarding Modern Encroachments on the Ancient Rights of Females, According to the Hindoo Law of Inheritance*, Calcutta, Printed at the Unitarian Press, 1822.

SELECT COMMITTEE, *Reports from Committees of the House of Commons. Vol. III, Miscellaneous, 1771 to 1773; and East India, 1772 & 1773. First-Fifth Report*, London, House of Commons, 1803.

SELECT COMMITTEE ON THE AFFAIRS OF THE EAST INDIA COMPANY, *Minutes of Evidence taken before the Honourable House of Commons*, London, E. Cox and Son, 1813.

SMITH Adam, *Recherches sur la nature et les causes de la richesse des nations*, traduit par Germain GARNIER et Adolphe BLANQUI, Paris, Flammarion, 1991 [1776], vol.2.

SMITH Adam, *Recherches sur la nature et les causes de la richesse des nations*, traduit par Germain GARNIER et Adolphe BLANQUI, Paris, Flammarion, 1991 [1776], vol.1.

STEELE Arthur, *The Law and Custom of Hindoo Castes*, 2^e éd., London, 1868.

STEUART Sir James, *The Principles of Money Applied to the Present State of the Coin of Bengal*, London, Composed for the Use of the Honourable the East-India Company, 1772.

STRANGE Thomas, *Hindu Law: principally with Reference to such Portions of it as concern the Administration of Justice, in the King's Courts, in India*, London, Parbury, Allen & Co., 1830, vol.2.

STRANGE Thomas, *Hindu Law: principally with Reference to such Portions of it as concern the Administration of Justice, in the King's Courts, in India*, London, Parbury, Allen & Co., 1830, vol.1.

SUPREME COUNCIL, BENGAL, *Original Minutes of the Governor-General and Council of Fort William on the Settlement and Collection of the Revenues of Bengal*, London, J. Debrett, 1782.

TABATABAI Ghulam Hussain Khan, *A Translation of the S̄eir Mutaqherin or, View of Modern Times*, traduit par [Hājī Mustafā] NOTA MANUS, Calcutta, Printed for the Translator, 1789, vol.2.

TARKAPAÑCĀNANA Jagannātha, *A Digest of Hindu Law on Contracts and Successions*, traduit par Henry T. COLEBROOKE, Calcutta, Printed at the Honourable Company's Press, 1798, vol.2.

TARKAPAÑCĀNANA Jagannātha, *A Digest of Hindu Law on Contracts and Successions*, traduit par Henry T. COLEBROOKE, Calcutta, Printed at the Honourable Company's Press, 1798, vol.1.

TUCKER Josiah, *A Sequel to Sir William Jones's Pamphlet on the Principles of Government*, Gloucester, R. Raikes, 1784.

TUPPER Charles Lewis, *Punjab Customary Law*, Calcutta, Office of the Superintendent of Government Printing, 1881.

VERELST Harry, *A View of the Rise, Progress, and Present State of the English Government in Bengal*, London, J. Nourse & alii., 1772.

WELLESLEY Richard, « Minute by the Marquis Wellesley, Containing His Reasons for the Establishment of a College in Bengal, Dated the 18th August, 1800 », in Thomas ROEBUCK (dir.), *The Annals of the College of Fort William*, Calcutta, Printed by Philip Pereira the Hindoostanee Press, 1819.

WILFORD Francis, « On Egypt and other countries adjacent to the Cálí River, or Nile of Ethiopia, from the ancient books of the Hindus », *Asiatick Researches*, 1792, n° 3, pp. 295-462.

WILKINS Charles, *A Grammar of the Sanskr̄ita Language*, London, W. Bulmer, 1808.

YOUNG Arthur, *Political Essays Concerning the Present State of the British Empire*, London, W. Strahan and T. Cadell, 1772.

Proceedings of the Committee of Circuit at Krishnagar and Kasimbazar 1772, Calcutta, Bengal Secretariat Book Depot, 1926.

Report of the Commissioners for the Investigation of Alleged Cases of Torture, in the Madras Presidency, Madras, H. Smith, 1855.

Minutes of Evidence taken before the Select Committee on the Affairs of the East India Company, and also an Appendix and Index, I, Public, London, House of Commons, 1832.

Minutes of Evidence taken before the Select Committee on the Affairs of the East India Company, and also an Appendix and Index, IV, Judicial, London, House of Commons, 1832.

Journals of the House of Commons, 1780-82, 1803, vol.38.

Sir Elijah Impey, Articles of Charge against, and Minutes of Evidence, IOR/L/PARL/2/8/71, London, House of Commons, 1787.

Le Bhagvat-Geeta ou dialogues de Kreeshna et d'Arjoon, traduit par Charles WILKINS et M. PARRAUD, Paris, Buisson, 1787.

Bhāgvāt-Geētā, or Dialogues of Krēṣhṇā and Ārjōṅ, traduit par Charles WILKINS, London, C. Nourse, 1785.

Report from the Committee to Whom the Petition of John Touchet and John Irving, Agents for the British Subjects Residing in the Provinces of Bengal, Bahar and Orissa, and Their Several Dependencies, Whose Name Are Subscribed to the Petition Thereinafter Set Forth ; and Also the Petition of Warren Hastings, Esq. ; Governor General, and of Philip Francis and Edward Wheler, Esqrs. Counsellors for the Government of the Presidency of Fort William, in Bengal ; and Also the Petition of the United Merchants of England, Trading to the East Indies ; Were Severally Referred, London, House of Commons, 1781.

« General Appendix », in *Touchet Report*, London, House of Commons, 1781.

« Patna Appendix », in *Touchet Report*, London, House of Commons, 1781.

« Dacca Appendix », in *Touchet Report*, London, House of Commons, 1781.

« Cossijurah Appendix », in *Touchet Report*, London, House of Commons, 1781.

The Bengal Appendix, IOR/L/PARL/2/9b, British Library, 1781.

« Extract of the Proceedings of the Governor-General and Council at Fort-William in Bengal, in Their Revenue Department, on Special Business, March 9, 1780 », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Letter from George Bogle, Esq; to the Governor-General and Council at Fort-William, Resigning His Office of Commissioner of Law-Suits to the Company », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« The Humble Petition of the British Subjects, Residing in the Provinces of Bengal, Bahar and Orissa, and Their Several Dependencies », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Translation of a Petition from the Renters of Farms of the Patna Province, stating the innumerable Hardships they suffer by being made liable to the Jurisdiction of the Supreme Court of Judicature at Calcutta », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Remarks on the Petition of the Inhabitants of Bengal, Bahar, and Orissa to Parliament by the Gentlemen of the Committee at Calcutta, Appointed to Transmit the Petition to England, and Transact the Business Appertaining Thereto », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Petition of Warren Hastings, Esq.; Governor General, and of Philip Francis, and Edward Wheler, Esquires, Counsellors for the Government of the Presidency of Fort William in Bengal to the Commons of Great Britain, in Parliament assembled », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Translation of a Persian Petition from the Native Inhabitants of the Subah Azeemabad to the King », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Letter from the Committee of the British Subjects Residing in Bengal, to the Right Honourable Lord North, dated Calcutta May 25, 1779 », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Letter from the Court of Directors to the Right Honourable Lord Weymouth, dated November 19, 1777 », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Petition of the United Company of Merchants trading to the East Indies », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

« Letter from the Governor General and Council to the Court of Directors, dated January 25, 1780 », in *The Several Petitions of the British Inhabitants of Bengal*, London, 1780.

Proceedings of the Governor and Council at Fort William, respecting the Administration of Justice amongst the Natives in Bengal, London, 1774.

Littérature secondaire

ABBASI Muhammad, « Shari‘a and State Law », *Journal of Law, Religion and State*, 2014, vol. 3, pp. 124-138.

AHMAD Asma Sharif, *The British Enlightenment and Ideas of Empire in India 1756-1773*, PhD Dissertation, Queen Mary University of London, 2005.

AHMAD Irfan, « Recognizing Hindu Orientalism », *Journal of Political Ideologies*, 2023, vol. 28, pp. 1-21.

AHMED Siraj, « The Theater of the Civilized Self: Edmund Burke and the East India Trials », *Representations*, 2002, vol. 78, n° 1, pp. 28-55.

ALAM Muzaffar, « The Culture and Politics of Persian in Precolonial Hindustan », in Sheldon POLLOCK (dir.), *Literary Cultures in History*, Berkeley and Los Angeles, University of California Press, 2003, pp. 131-198.

ALAM Muzaffar et SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *Writing the Mughal World: Studies on Culture and Politics*, New York, Columbia University Press, 2012.

ALTHUSSER Louis, *Montesquieu, la politique et l'histoire*, Presses universitaires de France, 1959.

ANDERSON Benedict, *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*, London, Verso, 1983.

ANDERSON Michael R., « Islamic Law and the Colonial Encounter in British India », in David ARNOLD et Peter ROBB (dirs.), *Institutions and Ideologies*, Curzon Press, 1993, pp. 165-185.

APP Urs, *The Birth of Orientalism*, Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press, 2010.

ARASARATNAM Sinnappah, « Trade and Political Dominion in South India, 1750-1790: Changing British-Indian Relationships », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1979, vol. 13, n° 1, pp. 19-40.

ARMITAGE David, « John Locke, Carolina, and the Two Treatises of Government », *Political Theory*, 2004, vol. 32, n° 5, pp. 602-627.

ARMITAGE David, *The Ideological Origins of the British Empire*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2000.

ARNOLD David, « Hunger in the Garden of Plenty: The Bengal Famine of 1770 », in Alessa JOHNS (dir.), *Dreadful Visitations: Confronting Natural Catastrophe in the Age of Enlightenment*, London - New York, Routledge, 1999, pp. 81-111.

ARNOLD David, *Colonizing the Body: State Medicine and Epidemic Disease in Nineteenth-Century India*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1993.

ARNOLD David, *Police Power and Colonial Rule: Madras, 1859-1947*, Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1986.

ASAD Talal, « Two European Images of Non-European Rule », in Talal ASAD (dir.), *Anthropology and the Colonial Encounter*, London, Ithaca Press, 1973, pp. 103-120.

ASSMANN Jan, *La Mémoire culturelle : Écriture, souvenir et imaginaire politique dans les civilisations antiques*, traduit par Diane MEUR, Paris, Aubier, 2010.

AXWORTHY Michael, « The Army of Nader Shah », *Iranian Studies*, 2007, vol. 40, n° 5, pp. 635-646.

AYLMER G. E., « From Office-Holding to Civil Service: The Genesis of Modern Bureaucracy », *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society*, 1980, vol. 30, pp. 91-108.

BALANDIER Georges, « La situation coloniale : approche théorique », *Cahiers internationaux de sociologie*, 1951, vol. 11, n° 1, pp. 44-79.

BANAJI Shakuntala, « Vigilante Publics: Orientalism, Modernity and Hindutva Fascism in India », *Javnost - The Public*, 2 octobre 2018, vol. 25, n° 4, pp. 333-350.

BANDOPADHYAY Saptarishi, *All is Well: Catastrophe and the Making of the Normal State*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2022.

BANERJEE Sumanta, *The Wicked City: Crime and Punishment in Colonial Calcutta*, New Delhi, Orient Blackswan, 2009.

BANERJEE Sumanta, *Under the Raj: Prostitution in Colonial Bengal*, New York, Monthly Review Press, 2000.

BARTHE Yannick, BLIC Damien DE, HEURTIN Jean-Philippe, LAGNEAU Éric, LEMIEUX Cyril, LINHARDT Dominique, MOREAU DE BELLAING Cédric, RÉMY Catherine et TROM Danny, « Sociologie pragmatique : mode d'emploi », *Politix*, 2013, vol. 103, n° 3, pp. 175-204.

BAYLY Christopher Alan, *Recovering Liberties: Indian Thought in the Age of Liberalism and Empire*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2012.

BAYLY Christopher Alan, « The First Age of Global Imperialism, c. 1760–1830 », *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History*, 1998, vol. 26, n° 2, pp. 28-47.

BAYLY Christopher Alan, *Origins of Nationality in South Asia: Patriotism and Ethical Government in the Making of Modern India*, Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1998.

BAYLY Christopher Alan, *Empire and Information: Intelligence Gathering and Social Communication in India, 1780-1870*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1996.

BAYLY Christopher Alan, *Imperial Meridian: The British Empire and the World, 1780-1830*, London - New York, Longman, 1989.

- BAYLY Christopher Alan, *Indian Society and the Making of the British Empire*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1988.
- BAYLY Christopher Alan, *Rulers, Townsmen and Bazaars: North Indian Society in the Age of British Expansion, 1770-1870*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1983.
- BAYLY Susan, *Caste, Society and Politics in India from the Eighteenth Century to the Modern Age*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1999.
- BEAGLEHOLE T. H., *Thomas Munro and the Development of Administrative Policy in Madras 1792-1818*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1966.
- BENTON Lauren, *Law and Colonial Cultures: Legal Regimes in World History, 1400-1900*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- BENTON Lauren, « Colonial Law and Cultural Difference: Jurisdictional Politics and the Formation of the Colonial State », *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 1999, vol. 41, n° 3, pp. 563-588.
- BENTON Lauren A, *A Search for Sovereignty: Law and Geography in European Empires, 1400-1900*, Cambridge; New York, Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- BENVENISTE Émile, *Problèmes de linguistique générale I*, Paris, Gallimard, 1966.
- BERG Maxine, GOTTMANN Felicia, HODACS Hanna et NIERSTRASZ Chris (dirs.), *Goods from the East 1600-1800: Trading Eurasia*, Houndmills, Basingstoke, Palgrave Macmillan, 2015.
- BERGSON Henri, *La Pensée et le mouvant*, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 1998 [1934].
- BERMAN Harold, *Droit et Révolution, II. L'Impact des réformes protestantes sur la tradition juridique occidentale*, traduit par Alain WIJFFELS, Paris, Fayard, 2011 [2003].
- BERTRAND Romain, *L'Histoire à parts égales : Récits d'une rencontre, Orient-Occident (XVI^e-XVII^e siècle)*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 2011.
- BHABHA Homi K., « Of Mimicry and Man: The Ambivalence of Colonial Discourse », in *The Location of Culture*, London - New-York, Routledge, 1994.
- BHATTACHARYYA-PANDA Nandini, *Appropriation and Invention of Tradition: The East India Company and Hindu Law in Early Colonial Bengal*, New Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2008.
- BLIC Damien DE et LEMIEUX Cyril, « Le scandale comme épreuve. Éléments de sociologie pragmatique », *Politix*, 2005, vol. 71, n° 3, pp. 9-38.
- BOLTANSKI Luc et CHIAPELLO Ève, *Le Nouvel Esprit du capitalisme*, Paris, Gallimard, 1999.
- BOLTANSKI Luc, CLAVERIE Élisabeth, OFFENSTADT Nicolas et VAN DAMME Stéphane (dirs.), *Affaires, scandales et grandes causes : de Socrate à Pinochet*, Paris, Stock, 2007.
- BOLTANSKI Luc et THÉVENOT Laurent, *De la justification : les économies de la grandeur*, Paris, Gallimard, 1991.

BOUMEDIENE Samir, *La Colonisation du savoir : Une histoire des plantes médicinales du « Nouveau monde »*, Vaulx-en-Velin, Les Éditions des mondes à faire, 2016.

BOURDIEU Pierre, *Sur l'État : Cours au Collège de France, 1989-1992*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 2011.

BOURDIEU Pierre, *Méditations pascaliennes*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1997.

BOURDIEU Pierre, *Le Sens pratique*, Paris, Éditions de Minuit, 1980.

BOURDIEU Pierre, *Esquisse d'une théorie de la pratique*, Genève - Paris, Droz, 1972.

BOURKE Richard, *Empire & Revolution: The Political Life of Edmund Burke*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2017.

BOWEN Huw V., *The Business of Empire: The East India Company and Imperial Britain, 1756–1833*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2005.

BOWEN Huw V., « British India, 1765–1813: The Metropolitan Context », in Peter James MARSHALL et Alaine LOW (dirs.), *The Oxford History of the British Empire*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1998, vol.2, pp. 530-551.

BOWEN Huw V., *Revenue and Reform: the Indian Problem in British Politics 1757-1773*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1991.

BOWEN Huw V., « The 'Little Parliament': The General Court of the East India Company, 1750–1784 », *The Historical Journal*, 1991, vol. 34, n° 4, pp. 857-872.

BOWEN Huw V., « A Question of Sovereignty? The Bengal Land Revenue Issue, 1765–67 », *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History*, 1988, vol. 16, n° 2, pp. 155-176.

BOWEN Huw V., « Lord Clive and Speculation in East India Company Stock, 1766 », *The Historical Journal*, 1987, vol. 30, n° 4, pp. 905-920.

BRAHAMI Frédéric, *La Raison du peuple : un héritage de la Révolution française, 1789-1848*, Paris, Les Belles lettres, 2016.

BREWER John, *The Sinews of Power: War, Money, and the English State*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 1990.

BRIANT Pierre, *Alexandre des Lumières : fragments d'histoire européenne*, Paris, Gallimard, 2012.

BRONKHORST Johannes, *How the Brahmins Won: from Alexander to the Guptas*, Leiden, Brill, 2016.

BURBANK Jane et COOPER Frédérick, *Empires. De la Chine ancienne à nos jours*, Paris, Payot, 2011 [2010].

BURBANK Jane et COOPER Frederick, « Rules of Law, Politics of Empire », in Lauren A. BENTON et Richard Jeffrey ROSS (dirs.), *Legal Pluralism and Empires, 1500-1850*, New York, New York University Press, 2013.

BURGHART Richard, « Hierarchical Models of the Hindu Social System », *Man*, 1978, vol. 13, n° 4, pp. 519-536.

BURKE Edmund, *The Writings and Speeches of Edmund Burke, Vol. 6: India: The Launching of the Hastings Impeachment: 1786-1788*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1991.

BURKE Edmund, *The Writings and Speeches of Edmund Burke, Vol. 5. India, Madras and Bengal: 1774–1785*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1981.

CAHEN Fabrice, *Le Nombre des hommes. La mesure de la population et ses enjeux (XVI^e-XXI^e siècle)*, Paris, Classiques Garnier, 2022.

CAIN P. J. et HOPKINS A. J., *British Imperialism, 1688-2015*, 3^e éd., London, Routledge, 2015.

CAMPBELL John, « Entre le "siècle de Louis XIV" et le siècle des Lumières : la rhétorique voltairienne à l'œuvre », *Littératures classiques*, 2011, vol. 76, n° 3, pp. 85-97.

CANNADINE David, *Ornamentalism: How the British Saw Their Empire*, London, Penguin Books, 2001.

CANNON Garland, *The Life and Mind of Oriental Jones*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1990.

CARSON Penelope, *The East India Company and Religion, 1698-1858*, Woodbridge, The Boydell Press, 2012.

CASTEL Pierre-Henri, *La Fin des coupables: suivi du Cas Paramord*, Paris, Les Éditions d'Ithaque, 2012.

CASTELNAU-L'ESTOILE Charlotte de et MALDAVSKY Aliocha, « Religions », in Cécile VIDAL (dir.), *Une Histoire sociale du Nouveau Monde*, Paris, Éditions de l'EHESS, 2021, pp. 199-230.

CAUSSAT Pierre, ADAMSKI Dariusz et CRÉPON Marc (dirs.), *La Langue, source de la nation : Messianismes séculiers en Europe centrale et orientale du XVIII^e au XX^e siècle*, Hayen, Mardaga, 1999.

CAVE Terence, « Ancients and Moderns: France », in Glyn P. NORTON (dir.), *The Cambridge History of Literary Criticism: The Renaissance*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1999, vol.3, pp. 417-425.

CÉSAIRE Aimé, *Discours sur le colonialisme*, Paris, Présence Africaine [1950], 2004.

CHAKRABARTY Dipesh, *Provincialiser l'Europe : la pensée postcoloniale et la différence historique*, traduit par Olivier RUCHET et Nicolas VIEILLESZAZES, Paris, Éditions Amsterdam, 2009 [2000].

CHATTERJEE Kumkum, « Scribal Elites in Sultanate and Mughal Bengal », *The Indian Economic & Social History Review*, 2010, vol. 47, n° 4, pp. 445-472.

CHATTERJEE Kumkum, « History as Self-Representation: The Recasting of a Political Tradition in Late Eighteenth-Century Eastern India », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1998, vol. 32, n° 4, pp. 913-948.

CHATTERJEE Nandini, « Reflections on Religious Difference and Permissive Inclusion in Mughal Law », *Journal of Law and Religion*, 2014, vol. 29, n° 3, pp. 396-415.

CHATTERJEE Partha (dir.), *Texts of Power: Emerging Disciplines in Colonial Bengal*, Minneapolis - London, University of Minnesota Press, 1995.

CHATTERJEE Partha, *The Nation and its Fragments: Colonial and Postcolonial Histories*, Princeton, N.J., Princeton University Press, 1993.

CHATTERJEE Partha, *Nationalist Thought and the Colonial World: A Derivative Discourse?*, London, Zed Books, 1986.

CHAUDHURI K. N., *The Trading World of Asia and the English East India Company: 1660-1760*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1978.

CLARK Longueville (dir.), *The Rules and Orders of the Supreme Court of Judicature at Fort William in Bengal*, Calcutta, S. Smith & Co, 1829.

COHN Bernard S., « Représenter l'autorité dans l'Inde victorienne », in Eric HOBBSBAWM et Terence RANGER (dirs.), *L'Invention de la tradition*, traduit par Christine VIVIER, Paris, Éditions Amsterdam, 2006 [1983], pp. 177-223.

COHN Bernard S., *Colonialism and its Forms of Knowledge: The British in India*, Princeton (N.J.), Princeton University Press, 1996.

COHN Bernard S., *An Anthropologist among the Historians and Other Essays*, Delhi - Oxford - New York, Oxford University Press, 1987.

COLLEY Linda, *Britons: Forging the Nation, 1707-1837*, New Haven and London, Yale University Press, 1992.

COMÍN Francisco Comín, YUN-CASALILLA Bartolomé et O'BRIEN Patrick K. (dirs.), *The Rise of Fiscal States: A Global History, 1500–1914*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2012.

CONNORS Richard, « 'The Grand Inquest of the Nation': Parliamentary Committees and Social Policy in Mid-Eighteenth-Century England », *Parliamentary History*, 1995, vol. 14, n° 3, pp. 285-313.

COOPER Frederick, *Le Colonialisme en question: Théorie, connaissance, histoire*, traduit par Christian JEANMOUGIN, Paris, Payot, 2010 [2005].

CRONK Nicholas, *Voltaire: A Very Short Introduction*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2017.

DALRYMPLE William, *Anarchie: L'implacable ascension de l'East India Company*, traduit par France CAMUS-PICHON, Lausanne, Les Éditions Noir sur Blanc, 2021 [2019].

DALRYMPLE William, *Le dernier Moghol*, traduit par France CAMUS-PICHON, Lausanne, Les Éditions Noir sur Blanc, 2008 [2007].

DALRYMPLE William, *Le Moghol blanc*, traduit par France CAMUS-PICHON, Montricher, Les Éditions Noir sur Blanc, 2005 [2002].

DAMASCENO FONSECA Claudia et MORELLI Federica, « Territoire et propriété », in Cécile VIDAL (dir.), *Une Histoire sociale du Nouveau Monde*, Paris, Éditions de l'EHESS, 2021, pp. 137-168.

DASTON Lorraine et GALISON Peter, *Objectivité*, traduit par Sophie RENAUT et Hélène QUINIOU, Dijon, Presses du Réel, 2012 [2007].

DATTA Rajat, *Society, Economy, and the Market: Commercialization in Rural Bengal, c. 1760-1800*, New Delhi, Manohar, 2000.

DAVIS Donald R., « Centres of Law: Duties, Rights and Jurisdictional Pluralism in Medieval India », in Paul DRESCH et Hannah SKODA (dirs.), *Legalism: Anthropology and History*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2012, pp. 85-113.

DAVIS Donald R., « Introduction », in ROCHER Ludo, *Studies in Hindu Law and Dharmasāstra*, London - New York, Anthem Press, 2012.

DAVIS Donald R., « Law in the Mirror of Language », in Thomas R. TRAUTMANN (dir.), *The Madras School of Orientalism*, New Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2009, pp. 288-309.

DAVIS Donald R., « Intermediate Realms of Law: Corporate Groups and Rulers in Medieval India », *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient*, 2005, vol. 48, n° 1, pp. 92-117.

DAVIS Donald R., « Recovering the Indigenous Legal Traditions of India: Classical Hindu Law in Practice in Late Medieval Kerala », *Journal of Indian Philosophy*, 1999, vol. 27, n° 3, pp. 159-213.

DAVIS Richard H., « Wilkins, Kasinatha, Hastings, and the First English Bhagavad Gītā », *International Journal of Hindu Studies*, 2015, vol. 19, n° 1, pp. 39-57.

DERRETT J. Duncan M., « Adoption in Hindu Law », in *Essays in Classical and Modern Hindu Law*, 3, Leiden, Brill, 1977, pp. 25-83.

DERRETT J. Duncan M., « J. H. Nelson: A Forgotten Administrator-Historian of India », in *Essays in Classical and Modern Hindu Law*, 2, Leiden, Brill, 1977, pp. 404-424.

DERRETT J. Duncan M., *Religion, Law and the State in India*, London, Faber and Faber, 1968.

DERRETT J. Duncan M., « “Justice, Equity and Good Conscience” », in *Changing Law in Developing Countries*, London, G. Allen and Unwin, 1963, pp. 114-153.

DERRETT J. Duncan M., « The Administration of Hindu Law by the British », *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 1961, vol. 4, n° 1, pp. 10-52.

DERRETT J. Duncan M., « Factum Valet: The Adventures of a Maxim », *The International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 1958, vol. 7, n° 2, pp. 280-302.

- DERRETT J. Duncan M., « Hindu Law: The Dharmaśāstra and Anglo-Hindu Law », *Zeitschrift für vergleichende Rechtswissenschaft*, 1956, n° 58, pp. 199-245.
- DEVEREUX George et LOEB Edwin M., « Antagonistic Acculturation », *American Sociological Review*, 1943, vol. 8, n° 2, pp. 133-147.
- DEWAR David et FUNNELL Warwick, *A History of British National Audit: The Pursuit of Accountability*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2016.
- DIAMOND Jared, *De l'inégalité parmi les sociétés*, traduit par Pierre-Emmanuel DAUZAT, Paris, Gallimard, 2007 [1997].
- DIRKS Nicholas B., *The Scandal of Empire: India and the Creation of Imperial Britain*, Harvard, Harvard University Press, 2009.
- DIRKS Nicholas B., *Castes of Mind: Colonialism and the Making of Modern India*, Princeton, N.J., Princeton University Press, 2001.
- DONIGER Wendy, *The Hindus: An Alternative History*, New York, Penguin Books, 2010.
- DONIGER Wendy, « Rationalizing the Irrational Other: “Orientalism” and the Laws of Manu », *New Literary History*, 1992, vol. 23, n° 1, pp. 25-43.
- DRAYTON Richard, *Nature's Government: Science, Imperial Britain, and the “Improvement” of the World*, New Haven and London, Yale University Press, 2000.
- DRAYTON Richard, « Knowledge and Empire », in Peter James MARSHALL (dir.), *The Oxford History of the British Empire: Volume II: The Eighteenth Century*, Oxford University Press, 1998, pp. 231-252.
- DUCHET Michèle, *Anthropologie et histoire au siècle des Lumières*, Paris, Albin Michel, 1995 [1971].
- DUMONT Louis, *Homo hierarchicus. Le système des castes et ses implications*, Paris, Gallimard, 1966.
- DURKHEIM Émile, *Les Formes élémentaires de la vie religieuse : le système totémique en Australie*, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 2005 [1912].
- DURKHEIM Émile, *Les Règles de la méthode sociologique*, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 2002 [1895].
- DURKHEIM Émile, « La contribution de Montesquieu à la constitution de la science sociale », in *Montesquieu et Rousseau: précurseurs de la sociologie*, M. Rivière, 1966 [1892], pp. 25-114.
- DWIVEDI Divya et MOHAN Shaj, *Indian Philosophy, Indian Revolution: On Caste and Politics*, London, Hurst & Company, 2024.
- EDELSTEIN Dan, *The Enlightenment: A Genealogy*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2010.

EHRlich Joshua, *The East India Company and the Politics of Knowledge*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2023.

ERIKSON Emily, *Between Monopoly and Free Trade: The English East India Company, 1600-1757*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2014.

ESTEBAN Javier Cuenca, « The British Balance of Payments, 1772-1820: India Transfers and War Finance », *The Economic History Review*, 2001, vol. 54, n° 1, pp. 58-86.

EWALD François, « Un pouvoir sans dehors », in *Michel Foucault philosophe. Rencontre internationale*, Paris, Seuil, 1989, pp. 196-202.

FERGUSON Wallace K., *La Renaissance dans la pensée historique*, traduit par Jacques MARTY, Paris, Payot & Rivages, 2008.

FEUCHTWANG Stephan, « The Discipline and its Sponsors », in Talal ASAD (dir.), *Anthropology and the Colonial Encounter*, London, Ithaca Press, 1973, pp. 71-102.

FISCHER-TINÉ Harald et MANN Michael (dirs.), *Colonialism as Civilizing Mission: Cultural Ideology in British India*, London, Anthem Press, 2004.

FISHER Michael H., « Indirect Rule in the British Empire: The Foundations of the Residency System in India (1764-1858) », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1984, vol. 18, n° 3, pp. 393-428.

FITZMAURICE Andrew, *Sovereignty, Property and Empire, 1500-2000*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2014.

FITZMAURICE Andrew, « Moral Uncertainty in the Dispossession of Native Americans », in Peter C. MANCALL (dir.), *The Atlantic World and Virginia, 1550-1624*, University of North Carolina Press, 2007, pp. 383-409.

FLEMING Christopher T., *Ownership and Inheritance in Sanskrit Jurisprudence*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2020.

FLETCHER Frank Thomas Herbert, *Montesquieu and English Politics, 1750-1800*, London, E. Arnold & Co., 1939.

FORCE James E. et POPKIN Richard H., *Essays on the Context, Nature, and Influence of Isaac Newton's Theology*, Dordrecht - Boston, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1990.

FOUCAULT Michel, *Leçons sur la volonté de savoir. Cours au Collège de France, 1970-1971*, Paris, EHESS Gallimard Seuil, 2011.

FOUCAULT Michel, *Sécurité, territoire, population. Cours au Collège de France, 1977-1978*, Paris, Gallimard Seuil, 2004.

FOUCAULT Michel, *Naissance de la biopolitique : Cours au Collège de France, 1978-1979*, Paris, Gallimard-Seuil, 2004.

FOUCAULT Michel, *Le Pouvoir psychiatrique. Cours au Collège de France, 1973-1974*, Paris, Gallimard Seuil, 2003.

- FOUCAULT Michel, *Dits et écrits I*, Paris, Gallimard, 2001.
- FOUCAULT Michel, « Nietzsche, la généalogie, l'histoire », in *Dits et écrits I*, Paris, Gallimard, 2001, pp. 1003-1024.
- FOUCAULT Michel, « *Il faut défendre la société* » : *Cours au Collège de France, 1975-1976*, Paris, Gallimard - Seuil, 1997.
- FOUCAULT Michel, *La Volonté de savoir*, Paris, Gallimard, 1976.
- FOUCAULT Michel, *Surveiller et punir*, Paris, Gallimard, 1975.
- FOUCAULT Michel, *L'Archéologie du savoir*, Paris, Gallimard, 1969.
- FOUCAULT Michel, *Les Mots et les choses*, Paris, Gallimard, 1966.
- FRAAS Arthur Mitchell, « *They Have Travailed into a Wrong Latitude: » the Laws of England, Indian Settlements, and the British Imperial Constitution 1726-1773*, PhD Dissertation, Duke University, 2011.
- FRANKEL Oz, *States of Inquiry: Social Investigations and Print Culture in Nineteenth-Century Britain and the United States*, Baltimore, The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2006.
- FRANKLIN Michael J., *Orientalist Jones : Sir William Jones, Poet, Lawyer, and Linguist, 1746-1794*, Oxford - New York, Oxford University Press, 2011.
- FRANKLIN Michael J., « Introduction », in *Sacotalá ; on the Mystical Poetry of the Persians and Hindus ; Gītagóvinda*, London Tokyo, Ganesha publishing, 2001, pp. vii-xxxiii.
- FUNNELL Warwick, « The “Proper Trust of Liberty”: Economical Reform, the English Constitution and the Protections of Accounting During the American War of Independence », *Accounting History*, 2008, vol. 13, n° 1, pp. 7-32.
- GALANTER Marc, *Law and Society in Modern India*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1989.
- GANERI Jonardon, *The Lost Age of Reason: Philosophy in Early Modern India, 1450-1700*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2011.
- GANJIPOUR Anoush, *L'Ambivalence politique de l'islam : Pasteur ou Léviathan ?*, Paris, Seuil, 2021.
- GELLNER Ernest, *Nations and Nationalism*, Ithaca - New York, Cornell University Press, 1983.
- GHOSH Durba, *Sex and the Family in Colonial India: The Making of Empire*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2008.
- GIUNCHI Elisa, « The Reinvention of “Sharī‘a” under the British Raj: In Search of Authenticity and Certainty », *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 2010, vol. 69, n° 4, pp. 1119-1142.
- GORDON Stewart, « The Limited Adoption of European-Style Military Forces by Eighteenth Century Rulers in India », *The Indian Economic & Social History Review*, 1998, vol. 35, n° 3, pp. 229-245.

GRAMSCI Antonio, *Cahiers de prison*, traduit par Pierre LAROCHE et Claude PERRUS, Paris, Gallimard, 1992, vol.5.

GRAY Neil, *Orientalism Inverted: The Rise of « Hindu Nation »*, <https://www.metamute.org/editorial/articles/orientalism-inverted-rise-hindu-nation>, consulté le 29 octobre 2023.

GREENE Jack P., *Evaluating Empire and Confronting Colonialism in Eighteenth-Century Britain*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2013.

GROVE Richard H., *Green Imperialism: Colonial Expansion, Tropical Island Edens and the Origins of Environmentalism, 1600-1860*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2010.

GUHA Ranajit, *Dominance Without Hegemony: History and Power in Colonial India*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 1997.

GUHA Ranajit, « Not at Home in Empire », *Critical Inquiry*, 1997, vol. 23, n° 3, pp. 482-493.

GUHA Ranajit, *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1983.

GUHA Ranajit, « The Prose of Counterinsurgency », in *Subaltern Studies II*, New Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1983, pp. 1-42.

GUHA Ranajit, « On Some Aspects of the Historiography of Colonial India », in *Subaltern Studies I*, New Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1982, pp. 1-9.

GUHA Ranajit, *A Rule of Property for Bengal: An Essay on the Idea of Permanent Settlement*, Paris - La Haye, Mouton, 1963.

GUHA Sumit, « The Qazi, the Dharmadhikari and the Judge », in Gijs KRUIJTZER et Thomas ERTL (dirs.), *Law Addressing Diversity: Premodern Europe and India in Comparison (13th-18th Centuries)*, Berlin, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2017, pp. 97-115.

GUHA Sumit, « Serving the Barbarian to Preserve the Dharma: The Ideology and Training of a Clerical Elite in Peninsular India c. 1300-1800 », *The Indian Economic & Social History Review*, 2010, vol. 47, n° 4, pp. 497-525.

GUHA Sumit, « Speaking Historically: The Changing Voices of Historical Narration in Western India, 1400-1900 », *The American Historical Review*, 2004, vol. 109, n° 4, pp. 1084-1103.

GUPTA Bishnupriya, « Competition and Control in the Market for Textiles: Indian Weavers and the English East India Company in the 18th Century », in Giorgio RIELLO et Tirthankar ROY (dirs.), *How India Clothed the World: The World of South Asian Textiles, 1500-1850*, Leiden - Boston, Brill, 2009, pp. 281-305.

HALBFASS Wilhelm, *India and Europe: an Essay in Understanding*, Albany, N.Y., SUNY Press, 1988.

HALLIDAY Paul D., *Habeas Corpus – From England to Empire*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 2010.

HARLING Philip, *The Waning of "Old Corruption": The Politics of Economical Reform in Britain, 1779-1846*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1996.

HATCHER Brian A., « Sanskrit and the Morning After: The Metaphorics and Theory of Intellectual Change », *The Indian Economic & Social History Review*, 2007, vol. 44, n° 3, pp. 333-361.

HATCHER Brian A., « What's Become of the Pandit? Rethinking the History of Sanskrit Scholars in Colonial Bengal », *Modern Asian Studies*, 2005, vol. 39, n° 3, pp. 683-723.

HEATH Deana, *Colonial Terror: Torture and State Violence in Colonial India*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2021.

HIRSCHMAN Albert O., *Les Passions et les intérêts : Justifications politiques du capitalisme avant son apogée*, traduit par Pierre ANDLER, Paris, Presses Universitaires de France [1977], 2014.

HIRSCHMAN Albert O., *Exit, Voice, and Loyalty*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 1970.

HOBBSAWM Eric et RANGER Terence (dirs.), *L'Invention de la tradition*, traduit par Christine VIVIER, Paris, Éditions Amsterdam [1983], 2006.

HOEXTER Miriam, « Qàḍī, Muftī and Ruler: Their Roles in the Development of Islamic Law », in RON SHAHAM (dir.), *Law, Custom, and Statute in the Muslim World*, Leiden, Brill, 2007.

HOSSAIN Hameeda, *The Company Weavers of Bengal: The East India Company and the Organization of Textile Production in Bengal, 1750-1813*, Oxford - Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1988.

HUSSAIN Nasser, *The Jurisprudence of Emergency: Colonialism and the Rule of Law*, Ann Arbor, The University of Michigan Press, 2003.

JAIN Mahabir Prashad, *Outlines of Indian Legal History*, 3^e éd., Bombay, N. M. Tripathi, 1972.

JONES Kenneth W., *Socio-Religious Reform Movements in British India*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1989.

JUPP Peter, *The Governing of Britain, 1688-1848: The Executive, Parliament and the People*, New York, Routledge, 2006.

KAISER Wolfgang, « Justinian and the Corpus Iuris Civilis », in David JOHNSTON (dir.), *The Cambridge Companion to Roman Law*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2015, pp. 119-148.

KANWAR Shimona, « Orientalism-in-Reverse: Indian Nationalism in the Works of M.K. Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru », *Panjab University Research Journal. Arts*, 2005

KARSENTI Bruno, *D'une philosophie à l'autre*, Paris, Gallimard, 2013.

KARSENTI Bruno, *Moïse et l'idée de peuple : la vérité historique selon Freud*, Paris, Éditions du Cerf, 2012.

- KARSENTI Bruno, *L'Homme total*, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 1997.
- KAVIRAJ Sudipta, « The Sudden Death of Sanskrit Knowledge », *Journal of Indian Philosophy*, 2005, vol. 33, n° 1, pp. 119-142.
- KHAN Abdul Majed, *The Transition in Bengal, 1756-1775: A Study of Saiyid Muhammad Reza Khan*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1969.
- KIDDER Robert L., « Western Law in India », *Sociological Inquiry*, 1977, vol. 47, n° 3-4, pp. 155-180.
- KIDDER Robert L., « Courts and Conflict in an Indian City: A Study in Legal Impact », *Journal of Commonwealth Political Studies*, 1973, vol. 11, n° 2, pp. 121-139.
- KNIGHTS Mark, *Trust and Distrust: Corruption in Office in Britain and its Empire, 1600-1850*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2021.
- KOEBNER R., « Despot and Despotism: Vicissitudes of a Political Term », *Journal of the Warburg and Courtauld Institutes*, 1951, vol. 14, n° 3/4, pp. 275-302.
- KOJÈVE Alexandre, *La Notion de l'autorité*, Paris, Gallimard, 2019.
- KOLFF D. H. A., « The Indian and the British Law Machines », in J. A. de MOOR et W. J. MOMMSEN (dirs.), *European Expansion and Law*, Oxford, Berg, 1992, pp. 201-235.
- KOLSKY Elizabeth, *Colonial Justice in British India: White Violence and the Rule of Law*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- KOPF David, *British Orientalism and the Bengal Renaissance. The Dynamics of Indian Modernization, 1773-1835*, Berkeley, California University Press, 1969.
- KOSELLECK Reinhart, *Le Règne de la critique*, traduit par Hans HILDENBRAND, Paris, Éditions de Minuit [1959], 1979.
- KROEZE Ronald (dir.), *Anticorruption in History*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2020.
- KRUIJTZER Gijis et ERTL Thomas, « Introduction », in *Law Addressing Diversity: Premodern Europe and India in Comparison (13th-18th Centuries)*, Berlin, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2017, pp. 1-15.
- KUGLE Scott Alan, « Framed, Blamed and Renamed: The Recasting of Islamic Jurisprudence in Colonial South Asia », *Modern Asian Studies*, 2001, vol. 35, n° 2, pp. 257-313.
- KUHN Thomas S., *La Structure des révolutions scientifiques*, traduit par Laure MEYER, Paris, Flammarion, 1991 [1962].
- LACKNER Helen, « Colonial Administration and Social Anthropology: Eastern Nigeria 1920-1940 », in Talal ASAD (dir.), *Anthropology and the Colonial Encounter*, London, Ithaca Press, 1973, pp. 123-152.
- LARIVIERE Richard W., « Dharmaśāstra, custom, “real law” and “apocryphal” smṛtis », *Journal of Indian Philosophy*, 2004, vol. 32, n° 5/6.

LARIVIERE Richard W., « Justices and Paṇḍitas: Some Ironies in Contemporary Readings of the Hindu Legal Past », *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 1989, vol. 48, n° 4, pp. 757-769.

LATOUR Bruno, « Irréductions », in *Pasteur: guerre et paix des microbes*, Paris, La Découverte, 2011 [1984], pp. 235-349.

LATOUR Bruno, *La Fabrique du droit*, Paris, La Découverte, 2004.

LATOUR Bruno, *L'Espoir de Pandore: pour une version réaliste de l'activité scientifique*, traduit par Didier GILLE, Paris, La Découverte, 2001 [1999].

LATOUR Bruno, *Nous n'avons jamais été modernes: essai d'anthropologie symétrique*, Paris, La Découverte, 1991.

LATOUR Bruno et WOOLGAR Steve, *La Vie de laboratoire: La production des faits scientifiques*, La Découverte, 1996 [1979].

LAWSON Philip, « Parliament and the First East India Inquiry, 1767 », *Parliamentary History*, 1982, vol. 1, n° 1, pp. 99-114.

LAWSON Philip et PHILLIPS Jim, « “Our Execrable Banditti”: Perceptions of Nabobs in Mid-Eighteenth Century Britain », *Albion: A Quarterly Journal Concerned with British Studies*, 1984, vol. 16, n° 3, pp. 225-241.

LEES James, « “A Character to Lose”: Richard Goodlad, the Rangpur Dhing, and the Priorities of the East India Company's Early Colonial Administrators », *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 2015, vol. 25, n° 2, pp. 301-315.

LEFÈVRE Corinne, « Beyond Diversity: Mughal Legal Ideology and Politics », in Gijs KRUIJTZER et Thomas ERTL (dirs.), *Law Addressing Diversity: Premodern Europe and India in Comparison (13th-18th Centuries)*, Berlin, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2017, pp. 116-141.

LEFÈVRE Corinne, « State-building and the Management of Diversity in India (Thirteenth to Seventeenth Centuries) », *The Medieval History Journal*, 2013, vol. 16, n° 2, pp. 425-447.

LEFÈVRE Corinne, « Pouvoir et noblesse dans l'Empire moghol », *Annales. Histoire, Sciences Sociales*, 2007, vol. 62, n° 6, pp. 1287-1312.

LEMIEUX Cyril, *La Sociologie pragmatique*, Paris, La Découverte, 2018.

LEONARD Spencer A., « ‘The Capital Object of the Public’: The 1766-7 Parliamentary Inquiry into the East India Company », *The English Historical Review*, 2017, vol. 132, n° 558, pp. 1110-1148.

LÉVI-STRAUSS Claude, *Le Regard éloigné*, Paris, Plon, 1983.

LÉVI-STRAUSS Claude, *L'Homme nu*, Paris, Plon, 1971.

LÉVI-STRAUSS Claude, *Les Structures élémentaires de la parenté*, 2^e éd., Mouton De Gruyter, 1967 [1949].

LÉVI-STRAUSS Claude, *Anthropologie structurale*, Paris, Plon, 1958.

- LEVI-STRAUSS Claude, « La Politique étrangère d'une société primitive », *Politique étrangère*, 1949, vol. 14, n° 2, pp. 139-152.
- LIEBERMAN David, *The Province of Legislation Determined: Legal Theory in Eighteenth-Century Britain*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1989.
- LILTI Antoine, *L'Héritage des Lumières: Ambivalences de la modernité*, Paris, Seuil, 2019.
- LINGAT Robert, *Les Sources du droit dans le système traditionnel de l'Inde*, Paris - La Haye, Mouton & Co., 1967.
- LINHARDT Dominique et MOREAU DE BELLAING Cédric, « Ni guerre, ni paix. Dislocations de l'ordre politique et décantonements de la guerre », *Politix*, 2013, vol. 104, n° 4, pp. 7-23.
- MANI Lata, *Contentious Traditions: The Debate on Sati in Colonial India*, Berkeley, University of California Press, 1998.
- MANN Michael, « From Ledger to Budget: British Fiscal Imperialism, 1750-1800 », *Internationales Asienforum*, 2002, vol. 33, n° 3-4, pp. 247-270.
- MANTENA Rama, « The Question of History in Precolonial India », *History and Theory*, 2007, vol. 46, n° 3, pp. 396-408.
- MANTOVANI Dario, « More than Codes: Roman Ways of Organising and Giving Access to Legal Information », in Paul J. du PLESSIS, Clifford ANDO et Kaius TUORI (dirs.), *The Oxford Handbook of Roman Law and Society*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2016.
- MARQUET Julie, « La médiation des dubashes », *La Révolution française*, 2015, n° 8, pp. 1-20.
- MARSHALL Peter James, *The Making and Unmaking of Empires: Britain, India, and America c.1750-1783*, Oxford University Press, 2005.
- MARSHALL Peter James, « *A Free Though Conquering People* »: *Eighteenth-Century Britain and Its Empire*, Aldershot, Ashgate Variorum, 2003.
- MARSHALL Peter James, « The English in Asia to 1700 », in Nicholas CANNY (dir.), *The Oxford History of the British Empire*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2001, vol.1, pp. 264-285.
- MARSHALL Peter James, « The White Town of Calcutta Under the Rule of the East India Company », *Modern Asian Studies*, 2000, vol. 34, n° 2, pp. 307-331.
- MARSHALL Peter James, « The Making of an Imperial Icon: The Case of Warren Hastings », *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History*, 1999, vol. 27, n° 3, pp. 1-16.
- MARSHALL Peter James, « The British in Asia: Trade to Dominion, 1700-1765 », in Peter James MARSHALL et Alaine LOW (dirs.), *The Oxford History of the British Empire*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1998, vol.2, pp. 485-507.
- MARSHALL Peter James, « British Society in India under the East India Company », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1997, vol. 31, n° 1, pp. 89-108.

MARSHALL Peter James, « Parliament and Property Rights in the Late Eighteenth-Century British Empire », in Susan STAVES et John BREWER (dirs.), *Early Modern Conceptions of Property*, London - New York, Routledge, 1994, pp. 530-544.

MARSHALL Peter James, « The Whites of British India, 1780-1830: A Failed Colonial Society? », *The International History Review*, 1990, vol. 12, n° 1, pp. 26-44.

MARSHALL Peter James, *Bengal: the British Bridgehead, Eastern India, 1740-1828*, Cambridge - New York, Cambridge University Press, 1987.

MARSHALL Peter James, « Private British Trade in the Indian Ocean before 1800 », in Ashin Das GUPTA et Michael Naylor PEARSON (dirs.), *India and the Indian Ocean, 1500-1800*, Oxford University Press, 1987, pp. 276-300.

MARSHALL Peter James, « Western Arms in Maritime Asia in the Early Phases of Expansion », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1980, vol. 14, n° 1, pp. 13-28.

MARSHALL Peter James, « Masters and Banians in Eighteenth-Century Calcutta », in Blair B. KING et M. N. PEARSON (dirs.), *The Age of Partnership. Europeans in Asia before Domination*, Honolulu, University of Hawaii Press, 1979, pp. 191-214.

MARSHALL Peter James, *East Indian Fortunes: The British in Bengal in the Eighteenth Century*, Oxford, Clarendon press, 1976.

MARSHALL Peter James, « Warren Hastings as Scholar and Patron », in John BROMLEY, Peter DICKSON et Anne WHITEMAN (dirs.), *Statesmen, Scholars and Merchants*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1973, pp. 242-262.

MARSHALL Peter James, *Problems of Empire: Britain and India, 1757-1813*, London - New York, George Allen & Unwin - Barnes & Noble, 1968.

MARSHALL Peter James, « Indian Officials under the East India Company in the Eighteenth-Century Bengal », *Bengal Past and Present*, 1965, vol. 84, n° 158, pp. 95-120.

MARSHALL Peter James et WILLIAMS Glyndwr, *The Great Map of Mankind: Perceptions of New Worlds in the Age of Enlightenment*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 1982.

MAUSS Marcel, *La Nation*, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 2013.

MAUSS Marcel, « Essai sur le don », in *Sociologie et anthropologie*, Paris, Presses Universitaires de France, 1950, pp. 145-284.

MAUSS Marcel et DURKHEIM Émile, « De quelques formes primitives de classification », in *Essais de sociologie*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1971 [1903], pp. 162-230.

MCLANE John R., *Land and Local Kingship in Eighteenth-Century Bengal*, Cambridge University Press, 2002.

MEHTA Uday Singh, *Liberalism and Empire: a Study in Nineteenth-Century British Liberal Thought*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 1999.

- MENDELSON Oliver, « The Pathology of the Indian Legal System », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1981, vol. 15, n° 4, pp. 823-863.
- MISRA Bankey Bihari, *The Central Administration of the East India Company, 1773-1834*, Manchester, Manchester University Press, 1959.
- MITCHELL Timothy, *Colonising Egypt*, Berkeley - Oxford, University of California Press, 1991.
- MOIR Martin, « Kaghazi Raj: Notes on the Documentary Basis of Company Rule: 1773-1858 », *Indo-British Review*, 1993, vol. 21, n° 2, pp. 185-193.
- MONCKTON JONES Mary E., *Warren Hastings in Bengal 1772-1774*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1918.
- MUKHERJEE Soumyendra Nath, *Sir William Jones: a Study in Eighteenth Century British Attitudes to India*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1968.
- MUTHU Sankar, « Adam Smith's Critique of International Trading Companies: Theorizing "Globalization" in the Age of Enlightenment », *Political Theory*, 2008, vol. 36, n° 2, pp. 185-212.
- MUTHU Sankar, *Enlightenment Against Empire*, Princeton, N.J. - Oxford, Princeton University Press, 2003.
- NANDA Meera, *Postcolonial Theory and the Making of Hindu Nationalism: The Wages of Unreason*, London, Routledge, 2025.
- NANDA Meera, *Prophets Facing Backward: Postmodern Critiques of Science and Hindu Nationalism in India*, New Brunswick, NJ, Rutgers University Press, 2003.
- NÉE Émilie, OGER Claire et SITRI Frédérique, « Le rapport : opérativité d'un genre hétérogène », *Mots. Les langages du politique*, 2017, vol. 114, n° 2, pp. 9-24.
- NEILD-BASU Susan, « The Dubashes of Madras », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1984, vol. 18, n° 1, pp. 1-31.
- NICK ROBINS, *The Corporation That Changed the World: How the East India Company Shaped the Modern Multinational*, London - Ann Arbor, Pluto Press, 2012.
- NISBET Robert A., *La Tradition sociologique*, traduit par Martine AZUELOS, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 1984 [1966].
- NOGUES-MARCO Pilar, « Measuring Colonial Extraction: The East India Company's Rule and the Drain of Wealth (1757–1858) », *Capitalism: A Journal of History and Economics*, 2021, vol. 2, n° 1, pp. 154-195.
- O'BRIEN Patrick et GRIFFITHS Trevor, « Political Components of the Industrial Revolution: Parliament and the English Cotton Textile Industry, 1660-1774 », *The Economic History Review*, 1991, vol. 44, n° 3, pp. 395-423.

OCKO Jonathan et GILMARTIN David, « State, Sovereignty, and the People: A Comparison of the “Rule of Law” in China and India », *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 2008, vol. 68, n° 1, pp. 55-133.

OGBORN Miles, *Indian Ink: Script and Print in the Making of the English East India Company*, Chicago - London, University of Chicago Press, 2007.

O’HANLON Rosalind, « In the Presence of Witnesses: Petitioning and Judicial ‘Publics’ in Western India, Circa 1600-1820 », *Modern Asian Studies*, 2019, vol. 53, n° 1, pp. 52-88.

O’HANLON Rosalind, « Contested Conjunctures: Brahman Communities and “Early Modernity” in India », *The American Historical Review*, 2013, vol. 118, n° 3, pp. 765-787.

O’HANLON Rosalind, « Speaking from Siva’s Temple: Banaras Scholar Households and the Brahman ‘Ecumene’ of Mughal India », *South Asian History and Culture*, 2011, vol. 2, n° 2, pp. 253-277.

O’HANLON Rosalind, « The Social Worth of Scribes: Brahmins, Kāyasthas and the Social Order in Early Modern India », *The Indian Economic & Social History Review*, 2010, vol. 47, n° 4, pp. 563-595.

O’HANLON Rosalind, « Letters Home: Banaras Pandits and the Maratha Regions in Early Modern India », *Modern Asian Studies*, 2010, vol. 44, n° 2, pp. 201-240.

O’HANLON Rosalind et MINKOWSKI Christopher, « What Makes People Who they Are? Pandit Networks and the Problem of Livelihoods in Early Modern Western India », *The Indian Economic & Social History Review*, 2008.

O’HANLON Rosalind et WASHBROOK David, « Histories in Transition: Approaches to the Study of Colonialism and Culture in India », *History Workshop*, 1991, n° 32, pp. 110-127.

OLDHAM James, *English Common Law in the Age of Mansfield*, Chapel Hill - London, University of North Carolina Press, 2004.

OLIVELLE Patrick, *King, Governance, and Law in Ancient India: Kauṭilya’s Arthaśāstra*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2013.

OLIVELLE Patrick et DAVIS Donald R. (dirs.), *Hindu Law: a New History of Dharmasāstra*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2018.

ORAIN Arnaud, *Le monde confisqué. Essai sur le capitalisme de la finitude*, Paris, Flammarion, 2025.

PAGDEN Anthony, « Law, Colonization, Legitimation, and the European Background », in Christopher TOMLINS et Michael GROSSBERG (dirs.), *The Cambridge History of Law in America: Volume 1: Early America (1580–1815)*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2008, pp. 1-31.

PAGDEN Anthony, *The Fall of Natural Man: the American Indian and the Origins of Comparative Ethnology*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1982.

- PARTHASARATHI Prasanna, *The Transition to a Colonial Economy: Weavers, Merchants and Kings in South India, 1720-1800*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2001.
- PASCAL Blaise, *Pensées*, Paris, Flammarion, 2008.
- PATTERSON Orlando, *Slavery and Social Death: A Comparative Study*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 1982.
- PERROT Jean-Claude, *Une Histoire intellectuelle de l'économie politique, XVII^e-XVIII^e siècle*, Paris, Éditions de l'EHESS, 1992.
- PHILIPS C. H. (dir.), *The Correspondence of Lord William Cavendish Bentinck*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1977, vol.2.
- PHILLIPS Andrew et SHARMAN J. C., *Outsourcing Empire: How Company-States Made the Modern World*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2020.
- PICKETT Catherine, *Bibliography of the East India Company: Books, Pamphlets and Other Materials Printed Between 1600 and 1785*, London, British Library, 2011.
- PIERCE Steven et RAO Anupama, *Discipline and the Other Body: Correction, Corporeality, Colonialism*, Durham, Duke University Press, 2006.
- PITTS Jennifer, *Naissance de la bonne conscience coloniale*, Ivry-sur-Seine, Éditions de l'Atelier, 2008 [2005].
- POCOCK John Greville Agard, *L'Ancienne Constitution et le droit féodal*, traduit par Sabine REUNGOAT et Michèle VIGNAUX, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 2000 [1957].
- POCOCK John Greville Agard, *Vertu, commerce et histoire : essais sur la pensée et l'histoire politique au XVIII^e siècle*, traduit par Hélène AJI, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 1998 [1985].
- POCOCK John Greville Agard, *Le Moment machiavélien : la pensée politique florentine et la tradition républicaine atlantique*, traduit par Luc BOROT, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 1997 [1975].
- POLANYI Karl, *La Grande Transformation : aux origines politiques et économiques de notre temps*, traduit par Catherine MALAMOUD et Maurice ANGENO, Paris, Gallimard, 1983 [1944].
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « The Revelation of Tradition: Śruti, Smṛti, and the Sanskrit Discourse of Power », in Federico SQUARCINI (dir.), *Boundaries, Dynamics and Construction of Traditions In South Asia*, London - New-York, Anthem Press, 2011, pp. 41-61.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « The Languages of Science in Early Modern India », in Sheldon POLLOCK (dir.), *Forms of Knowledge in Early Modern Asia*, Durham, N.C., Duke University Press, 2011, pp. 19-48.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « Pretextures of Time », *History and Theory*, 2007, vol. 46, n° 3, pp. 366-383.

- POLLOCK Sheldon, *The Language of the Gods in the World of Men: Sanskrit, Culture, and Power in Premodern India*, Berkeley, University of California Press, 2006.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, *The Ends of Man at the End of Premodernity*, Amsterdam, Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, 2005.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « The Death of Sanskrit », *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 2001, vol. 43, n° 2, pp. 392-426.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « India in the Vernacular Millennium: Literary Culture and Polity, 1000-1500 », *Daedalus*, 1998, vol. 127, n° 3, pp. 41-74.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « Deep Orientalism? », in Carol A. BRECKENRIDGE et Peter VAN DER VEER (dirs.), *Orientalism and the Postcolonial Predicament*, Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press, 1993.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « From Discourse of Ritual to Discourse of Power in Sanskrit Culture », *Journal of Ritual Studies*, 1990, vol. 4, n° 2, pp. 315-345.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « The Idea of Śāstra in Traditional India », in Anna Libera DALLAPICCOLA (dir.), *Shastric Traditions in Indian Arts*, Stuttgart, Steiner Verlag, 1989, pp. 17-26.
- POLLOCK Sheldon, « The Theory of Practice and the Practice of Theory in Indian Intellectual History », *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 1985, vol. 105, n° 3, pp. 499-519.
- POMERANZ Kenneth, *Une Grande Divergence : La Chine, l'Europe et la construction de l'économie mondiale*, traduit par Nora WANG et Mathieu ARNOUX, Paris, Albin Michel, 2010 [2000].
- POSTEMA Gerald J., *Bentham and the Common Law Tradition*, 2^e éd., Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2019 [1986].
- PRAKASH Om, « From Market-Determined to Coercition-Based: Textile Manufacturing in 18th Century Bengal », in Giorgio RIELLO et Tirthankar ROY (dirs.), *How India Clothed the World: The World of South Asian Textiles, 1500-1850*, Leiden - Boston, Brill, 2009, pp. 217-252.
- PRASAD Bisheshwar (dir.), *Fort William - India House Correspondence and Other Contemporary Papers Relating Thereto*, Delhi, National Archives of India, 1960, vol.6, Public, select and secret, 1770-1772.
- PRICE Pamela, « The “Popularity” of the Imperial Courts of Law », in J. A. de MOOR et W. J. MOMMSEN (dirs.), *European Expansion and Law*, Oxford, Berg, 1992, pp. 179-200.
- RAJ Kapil, « Régler les différends, gérer les différences : dynamiques urbaines et savantes à Calcutta au XVIII^e siècle », *Revue d'histoire moderne et contemporaine*, 2008, vol. 55-2, n° 2, pp. 70-100.
- RAJ Kapil, *Relocating Modern Science: Circulation and the Construction of Knowledge in South Asia and Europe, 1650-1900*, Basingstoke, Palgrave Macmillan, 2007.

- RAMAN Bhavani, *Document Raj: Writing and Scribes in Early Colonial South India*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2012.
- RANGER Terence, « The Invention of Tradition Revisited: The Case of Colonial Africa », in Terence RANGER et Olufemi VAUGHAN (dirs.), *Legitimacy and the State in Twentieth-Century Africa*, London, Palgrave Macmillan, 1993, pp. 62-111.
- RAO Velcheru Narayana, SHULMAN David Dean et SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *Textures of Time: Writing History in South India*, New York, Other Press, 2003.
- RAO Velcheru Narayana, SHULMAN David et SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, « A Pragmatic Response », *History and Theory*, 2007, vol. 46, n° 3, pp. 409-427.
- RAY Rajat Kanta, « Indian Society and the Establishment of British Supremacy, 1765–1818 », in Peter James MARSHALL et Alaine LOW (dirs.), *The Oxford History of the British Empire*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1998, vol.2, pp. 508-529.
- RAYNAUD Philippe, « La loi et la jurisprudence, des Lumières à la Révolution française », *Archives de philosophie du droit*, 1985, n° 30, pp. 61-72.
- REITAN E. A., « The Civil List in Eighteenth-Century British Politics: Parliamentary Supremacy versus the Independence of the Crown », *The Historical Journal*, 1966, vol. 9, n° 3, pp. 318-337.
- RICHARDS John F., « Fiscal states in Mughal and British India », in Francisco Comín COMÍN, Bartolomé YUN-CASALILLA et Patrick K. O'BRIEN (dirs.), *The Rise of Fiscal States: A Global History, 1500–1914*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2012, pp. 410-441.
- RICHTER Melvin, « The Comparative Study of Regimes and Societies », in Mark GOLDIE et ROBERT WOKLER (dirs.), *The Cambridge History of Eighteenth-Century Political Thought*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2006, pp. 147-171.
- RIELLO Giorgio et ROY Tirthankar (dirs.), *How India Clothed the World: The World of South Asian Textiles, 1500-1850*, Leiden - Boston, Brill, 2009.
- ROBB Peter, *Ancient Rights and Future Comfort: Bihar, the Bengal Tenancy Act of 1885, and British Rule in India*, Richmond, Surrey, Curzon Press, 1997.
- ROBERTS Clayton, « The Constitutional Significance of the Financial Settlement of 1690 », *The Historical Journal*, 1977, vol. 20, n° 1, pp. 59-76.
- ROCHER Ludo, *Studies in Hindu Law and Dharmasāstra*, London - New York, Anthem Press, 2012.
- ROCHER Ludo, « Introduction », in *Jīmūtavāhana's Dayabhaga: the Hindu law of inheritance in Bengal*, New York - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2002, pp. 3-50.
- ROCHER Ludo et ROCHER Rosane, *The Making of Western Indology: Henry Thomas Colebrooke and the East India Company*, Abingdon - New York, Routledge, 2012.

ROCHER Rosane, « Weaving Knowledge: Sir William Jones and Indian Pandits », in Garland CANNON et Kevin BRINE (dirs.), *Objects of Enquiry: the Life, Contributions, and Influences of Sir William Jones (1746-1794)*, New York - London, New York University Press, 1995.

ROCHER Rosane, « British Orientalism in the Eighteenth Century », in Carol A. BRECKENRIDGE et Peter VAN DER VEER (dirs.), *Orientalism and the Postcolonial Predicament*, Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press, 1993.

ROCHER Rosane, « The Career of Rādhākānta Tarkavāgīśa, an Eighteenth-Century Pandit in British Employ », *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 1989, vol. 109, n° 4, pp. 627-633.

ROCHER Rosane, *Orientalism, Poetry, and the Millennium: the Checkered Life of Nathaniel Brassey Halhed, 1751-1830*, Delhi, Motilal Banarsidass, 1983.

ROCHER Rosane, « New Data for the Biography of the Orientalist Alexander Hamilton », *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 1970, vol. 90, n° 3, pp. 426-448.

ROCHER Rosane, *Alexander Hamilton, 1762-1824. A Chapter in the Early History of Sanskrit philology*, New Haven, Conn., American Oriental Society, 1968.

ROY Tirthankar, « Rethinking the Origins of British India: State Formation and Military-fiscal Undertakings in an Eighteenth Century World Region », *Modern Asian Studies*, 2013, vol. 47, n° 4, pp. 1125-1156.

SAID Edward W., *L'Orientalisme : l'Orient créé par l'Occident*, traduit par Catherine MALAMOUD, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1997 [1978].

SALMON Gildas, « La révolution morphologique : Henry Sumner Maine et l'émergence de l'anthropologie juridique comme science de gouvernement dans l'Empire britannique », *Droit & philosophie*, 2024, n° 16, p. 85-116.

SALMON Gildas, « La réalité des normes : pour une histoire du gouvernement sociopolitique », in Isabelle ALFANDARY, Joseph COHEN, Sandra LAUGIER et Raphaël ZAGURY-ORLY (dirs.), *Où va la philosophie française ?*, Paris, Vrin, 2024, pp. 163-173.

SALMON Gildas, « Monothéisme et empire colonial. Les conditions théologiques du pluralisme juridique dans l'Inde britannique », in Anoush GANJIPOUR (dir.), *Monothéismes et politique*, Paris, CNRS Éditions, 2022, pp. 121-148.

SALMON Gildas, « Savoirs orientalistes et savoirs brahmaniques : une généalogie indo-européenne de la grammaire comparée », *Romantisme*, 2019, vol. 185, n° 3, pp. 26-37.

SALMON Gildas, « On Ontological Delegation. The Birth of Neoclassical Anthropology », in Pierre CHARBONNIER, Gildas SALMON et Peter SKAFISH (dirs.), *Comparative Metaphysics*, London, Rowman & Littlefield International, 2017, pp. 41-60.

SALMON Gildas, *Les Structures de l'esprit : Lévi-Strauss et les mythes*, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 2013.

SCHAUB Jean-Frédéric, *Pour une histoire politique de la race*, Paris, Seuil, 2015.

SCHAUB Jean-Frédéric et SEBASTIANI Silvia, *Race et histoire dans les sociétés occidentales (XV^e-XVIII^e siècle)*, Paris, Albin Michel, 2021.

SCHWAB Raymond, *La Renaissance orientale*, Paris, Payot, 2014 [1950].

SCOTT James C., *Zomia, ou l'art de ne pas être gouverné*, traduit par Frédéric JOLY et Olivier RUCHET, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 2013 [2009].

SEBASTIANI Silvia, *The Scottish Enlightenment: Race, Gender, and the Limits of Progress*, New York, Palgrave Macmillan, 2013.

SEN Sudipta, « Historian as Witness: Ghulam Husain Tabatabai and the Dawning of British Rule in India », in *India and Iran in the Long Durée*, Irvine, Brill, 2017, pp. 103-124.

SENELLART Michel, « La population comme signe du bon gouvernement », in André CHARRAK et Jean SALEM (dirs.), *Rousseau et la philosophie*, Paris, Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2019, pp. 189-212.

SHAPIN Steven, *Une Histoire sociale de la vérité : Science et mondanité dans l'Angleterre du XVII^e siècle*, traduit par Samuel COAVOUX et Alcime STEIGER, Paris, La Découverte, 2014 [1994].

SIDDIQUE Asheesh Kapur, « William Jones, Esq. », *Global Intellectual History*, 2023, pp. 102-108.

SIMMEL Georg, *L'Étranger*, traduit par Frédéric JOLY, Paris, Payot & Rivages, 2019.

SINGHA Radikha, « Civil Authority and Due Process », in Michael R. ANDERSON et Sumit GUHA (dirs.), *Changing Concepts of Rights and Justice in South Asia*, Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1998.

SINHA Samita, *Pandits in a Changing Environment: Centres of Sanskrit Learning in Nineteenth Century Bengal*, Calcutta, Sarat Book House, 1993.

SPECTOR Céline, *Montesquieu : Liberté, droit et histoire*, Paris, Michalon, 2010.

SPECTOR Céline, *Montesquieu : pouvoirs, richesses et sociétés*, Paris, Hermann, 2010.

SPECTOR Céline, *Montesquieu et l'émergence de l'économie politique*, Paris, Honoré Champion, 2006.

SPECTOR Céline, « Montesquieu, l'Europe et les nouvelles figures de l'empire », *Revue Montesquieu*, 2006, n° 8, pp. 17-42.

SPERBER Nathan et HOARE George, *Introduction à Antonio Gramsci*, Paris, La Découverte, 2013.

SPEZIALE Fabrizio, « Les traités persans sur les sciences indiennes : médecine, zoologie, alchimie », in Denis HERMANN et Fabrizio SPEZIALE (dirs.), *Muslim Cultures in the Indo-Iranian World*, Téhéran - Berlin, Institut Francais de Recherche en Iran - Klaus Schwarz Verlag, 2010.

SPIVAK Gayatri Chakravorty, *Les Subalternes peuvent-elles parler ?*, traduit par Jérôme VIDAL, Paris, Éditions Amsterdam, 2020 [1988].

SQUARCINI Federico, *Tradition, Veda and Law: Studies on South Asian Classical Intellectual Traditions*, Firenze, Società editrice fiorentina, 2008.

SRINIVAS Mysore Narasimhachar, « A Note on Sanskritization and Westernization », *The Far Eastern Quarterly*, 1956, vol. 15, n° 4, pp. 481-496.

SRINIVAS Mysore Narasimhachar, *Religion and Society Among the Coorgs of South India*, Clarendon Press, 1952.

SRIVASTAVA Swati, « Corporate Sovereign Awakening and the Making of Modern State Sovereignty: New Archival Evidence from the English East India Company », *International Organization*, 2022, vol. 76, n° 3, pp. 690-712.

STEIN Burton, *Thomas Munro: The Origins of the Colonial State and His Vision of Empire*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1989.

STEIN Burton, « State Formation and Economy Reconsidered: Part One », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1985, vol. 19, n° 3, pp. 387-413.

STEIN Peter, *Roman Law in European History*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1999.

STERN Philip, « Corporate Virtue: The Languages of Empire in Early Modern British Asia », *Renaissance Studies*, 2012, vol. 26, n° 4, pp. 510-530.

STERN Philip J., *The Company-State: Corporate Sovereignty and the Early Modern Foundation of the British Empire in India*, New York - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2011.

STOKES Eric, « Bureaucracy and Ideology: Britain and India in the Nineteenth Century », *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society*, 1980, vol. 30, pp. 131-156.

STOKES Eric, *The English Utilitarians and India*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1959.

STOLER Ann Laura et COOPER Frederick, *Repenser le colonialisme*, traduit par Christian JEANMOUGIN, Payot & Rivages, 2013 [1997].

STROUMSA Guy, *The Making of the Abrahamic Religions in Late Antiquity*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2015.

SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *Empires between Islam and Christianity, 1500-1800*, Albany, SUNY Press, 2019.

SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *Europe's India: Words, People, Empires, 1500-1800*, Cambridge, Mass., Harvard University Press, 2017.

SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *L'Empire portugais d'Asie, 1500-1700*, traduit par Marie-José CAPELLE, Paris, Seuil, 2013 [1993].

SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *Penumbra Visions: Making Politics in Early Modern South India*, Ann Arbor, University of Michigan Press, 2001.

SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay, *The Political Economy of Commerce: Southern India 1500-1650*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1990.

SUBRAMANIAN Lakshmi, « Baniyas and the British: The Role of Indigenous Credit in the Process of Imperial Expansion in Western India in the Second Half of the Eighteenth Century », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1987, vol. 21, n° 3, pp. 473-510.

SUTHERLAND Lucy Stuart, *The East India Company in Eighteenth-century Politics*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1952.

SUTHREN HIRST Jacqueline, « Who Are the Others? Three Moments in Sanskrit-Based Practice », in Nile GREEN et Mary SEARLE-CHATTERJEE (dirs.), *Religion, Language, and Power*, Routledge, 2008.

SWEETMAN Will, *Mapping Hinduism: "Hinduism" and the Study of Indian Religions, 1600-1776*, Halle, Verlag der Franckeschen Stiftungen zu Halle, 2003.

SYKES John, « Sykes, Sir Francis, first baronet », in *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography*, 2015.

TAMANAH Brian Z., *On the Rule of Law: History, Politics, Theory*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2004.

TAVAKOLI-TARGHI Mohamad, *Refashioning Iran: Orientalism, Occidentalism, and Historiography*, Basingstoke, Palgrave, 2001.

THOMAS Peter D. G., *The House of Commons in the Eighteenth Century*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1971.

THOMAS Yan, *Les Opérations du droit*, Paris, EHESS Gallimard Seuil, 2011.

THOMPSON Edward P., *Les Usages de la coutume. Traditions et résistances populaires en Angleterre*, traduit par Jean BOUTIER et Arundhati VIRMANI, Paris, Seuil, 2015 [1991].

THOMPSON Edward Palmer, *La Guerre des forêts : luttes sociales dans l'Angleterre du XVIII^e siècle*, traduit par Christophe JAQUET, Paris, La Découverte, 2014 [1975].

TILLY Charles, *Coercion, Capital and European States, A.D. 990 - 1992*, Cambridge, Mass., Wiley-Blackwell, 1992.

TILLY Charles, « War Making and State Making as Organized Crime », in Dietrich RUESCHEMEYER, Peter B. EVANS et Theda SKOCPOL (dirs.), *Bringing the State Back In*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1985, pp. 169-191.

TODOROV Tzvetan, *La Conquête de l'Amérique. La question de l'autre*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1982.

TORRANCE John, « Social Class and Bureaucratic Innovation: The Commissioners for Examining the Public Accounts 1780-1787 », *Past & Present*, 1978, n° 78, pp. 56-81.

TRAUTMANN Thomas R. (dir.), *The Madras School of Orientalism: Producing Knowledge in Colonial South India*, New Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2009.

TRAUTMANN Thomas R., *Languages and Nations: the Dravidian Proof in Colonial Madras*, Berkeley - London, University of California Press, 2006.

TRAUTMANN Thomas R., *Aryans and British India*, Berkeley - London, University of California Press, 1997.

TRAVERS Robert, *Empires of Complaints: Mughal Law and the Making of British India, 1765–1793*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2022.

TRAVERS Robert, « Indian Petitioning and Colonial State-Formation in Eighteenth-Century Bengal », *Modern Asian Studies*, janvier 2019, vol. 53, n° 1, pp. 89-122.

TRAVERS Robert, « British India as a Problem in Political Economy: Comparing James Steuart and Adam Smith », in Duncan KELLY (dir.), *Lineages of Empire: The Historical Roots of British Imperial Thought*, British Academy, 2009, pp. 137-160.

TRAVERS Robert, *Ideology and Empire in Eighteenth Century India*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2007.

TREVOR-ROPER Hugh, « La tradition des Highlands », in Eric HOBBSBAWM et Terence RANGER (dirs.), *L'Invention de la tradition*, traduit par Christine VIVIER, Paris, Éditions Amsterdam [1983], 2006, pp. 27-54.

TRUSCHKE Audrey, *Culture of Encounters: Sanskrit at the Mughal Court*, New York, Columbia University Press, 2016.

UEXKÜLL Jakob von, *Mondes animaux et monde humain*, traduit par Philippe MULLER, Paris, Pocket [1956], 2004.

VAUGHN James M., *The Politics of Empire at the Accession of George III: The East India Company and the Crisis and Transformation of Britain's Imperial State*, New Haven, Yale University Press, 2019.

VICZIANY Marika, « Imperialism, Botany and Statistics in Early Nineteenth-Century India: The Surveys of Francis Buchanan (1762-1829) », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1986, vol. 20, n° 4, pp. 625-660.

VIDAL Cécile, « Introduction », in Cécile VIDAL (dir.), *Une Histoire sociale du Nouveau Monde*, Paris, Éditions de l'EHESS, 2021, pp. 13-43.

VIDAL Cécile, « Travail », in Cécile VIDAL (dir.), *Une Histoire sociale du Nouveau Monde*, Paris, Éditions de l'EHESS, 2021, pp. 75-103.

VIDAL Cécile et SCHAUB Jean-Frédéric, « Ordre social », in Cécile VIDAL (dir.), *Une Histoire sociale du Nouveau Monde*, Paris, Éditions de l'EHESS, 2021, pp. 261-290.

WAGONER Phillip B., « Precolonial Intellectuals and the Production of Colonial Knowledge », *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 2003, vol. 45, n° 4, pp. 783-814.

WARBURTON William, *The Divine Legation of Moses Demonstrated on the Principle of a Religious Deist*, London, Fletcher Gyles, 1738, vol.1.

WASHBROOK David, « Law, State and Agrarian Society in Colonial India », *Modern Asian Studies*, 1981, vol. 15, n° 3, pp. 649-721.

WEBER Max, *La Domination*, traduit par Isabelle KALINOWSKI, Paris, La Découverte, 2013.

WEBER Max, *Sociologie du droit*, traduit par Jacques GROSCLAUDE, Paris, Presses universitaires de France, 2013.

WEBER Max, *L'Éthique protestante et l'esprit du capitalisme*, traduit par Isabelle KALINOWSKI, Paris, Flammarion, 2008.

WEISS MULLER Hannah, *Subjects and Sovereign: Bonds of Belonging in the Eighteenth-century British Empire*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2017.

WHELAN Frederick G., *Edmund Burke and India: Political Morality and Empire*, Pittsburgh, University of Pittsburgh Press, 1996.

WHITE Richard, *Le Middle Ground : Indiens, empires et républiques dans la région des Grands lacs, 1650-1815*, traduit par Frédéric COTTON, Toulouse, Anacharsis, 2009 [1991].

WILKINSON Callie, *Empire of Influence: The East India Company and the Making of Indirect Rule*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2023.

WILLIAMS Rina Verma, « Hindu Law as Personal Law: State and Identity in the Hindu Code Bills Debates, 1952-1956 », in Timothy LUBIN, Donald R. DAVIS et Jayanth K. KRISHNAN (dirs.), *Hinduism and Law: An Introduction*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2010, pp. 105-119.

WILSON Jon, *India Conquered: Britain's Raj and the Chaos of Empire*, London, Simon & Schuster, 2016.

WILSON Jon, *The Domination of Strangers: Modern Governance in Eastern India, 1780-1835*, Basingstoke, Palgrave Macmillan, 2010.

WILSON Jon E., « 'A Thousand Countries To Go To': Peasants and Rulers in Late Eighteenth-Century Bengal », *Past & Present*, 2005, vol. 189, n° 1, pp. 81-109.

WILSON Kathleen, « Empire of Virtue », in Lawrence STONE (dir.), *An Imperial State at War: Britain from 1689 to 1815*, London, Routledge, 1994, pp. 128-164.

WINTERBOTTOM Anna, *Hybrid Knowledge in the Early East India Company World*, Houndmills, Basingstoke, Palgrave Macmillan, 2016.

XAVIER Ângela Barreto et ŽUPANOV Ines G., *Catholic Orientalism : Portuguese Empire, Indian Knowledge (16th-18th centuries)*, New Delhi, Oxford University Press, 2015.

ZAMAN Muhammad Qasim, *The Ulama in Contemporary Islam: Custodians of Change*, Princeton, N.J., Princeton University Press, 2002.

ŽUPANOV Ines G., *Disputed Mission: Jesuit Experiments and Brahmanical Knowledge in 17th Century India*, New Delhi - Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1999.